

Infosheet: Poland

Based on NaturaConnect data

Background

Poland (capital Warsaw) covers a total of 311970.48 km² area, with protected areas currently spanning 39.51 % (123253.13 km²) of all land area, out of which 0.63 % (1979.44 km²) can be considered as strictly protected area.

Integrating a range of novel datasets, NaturaConnect results suggest to expand the protected area network up to 33.55 % (104662.22 km²) to better protected species, habitats and ecosystem services.

More Information: [CBD](#) [Protected Planet](#) [BISE](#)

■ Expansion Strict PA
 ■ Expansion PA
 ■ Existing Strict PA
 ■ Existing PA
 ■ Unprotected Areas

Figure: Existing and proposed consensus expansion priorities by the NaturaConnect project.

Performance Indicators

The NaturaConnect project has identified priority areas for expanding protected area networks across Europe to better conserve biodiversity. Each region and the proposed expansion areas are evaluated through a set of 'performance' indicators that reflect either potential benefits or risks of additional conservation or restoration action in these areas.

Performance indicators for current (inner polygon) and proposed expansion areas (outer polygon).

Relative difference in indicator values of target region (red) relative to other regions (grey points). Text indicates the difference in indicator value between the target region and the mean across all regions.

Source: International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis

Key recommendations

- Expansion of protected areas to cover at least 30% of the land area is recommended to effectively conserve biodiversity.
- Poland has significant potential for expanding strict protected areas.
- Connectivity between existing protected areas should be prioritized to enhance ecological networks and facilitate species movement.

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